

EFFECTIVE USE OF MULTIMEDIA IN VOCATIONAL SCHOOLS

Ko`chkinov Xudaybergan (TerAIRI kata o`qituvchi)

Niyazova Lola (Termiz kasb-xunar maktabi o`qituvchi)

Annotation: The article contains information on the effective use of multimedia in vocational schools. Some methodological recommendations for teaching were given.

Key words: English, teaching, vocabulary, classroom-oriented activity

Today, a truly revolutionary information process is taking place in the world. It should be emphasized that the development of the economy in society is carried out not through the circulation of goods, resources, and materials, but through the power of ideas and knowledge.

Such an opportunity is due to the advent of digital media services. The widespread use of multimedia tools in education is one of the urgent tasks of our time. In carrying out these tasks, along with expanding the range of knowledge and skills related to the use of multimedia technology, it is important to increase the quantity and quality of information resources. For example, by connecting to the Internet via your phone, you can access electronic databases, books and necessary information about a number of other political and social fields and even carry out commercial activities.

Information technology develops on the basis of scientific and technological achievements, especially basic sciences. It should be noted that it is important to continuously discuss this issue in the media to demonstrate the importance of IT for society. In this regard, a certain amount of experience has been accumulated in our republic.

The use of multimedia technologies in education has led to the emergence of new educational technologies and their specific forms based on the transmission of information and electronic media. Interactive computer programs and powerful multimedia systems are a perfect example. Despite the fact that the technical and technological tools used in the educational process are different, the quality of teaching can be high or satisfactory depending on the form and means of presentation of educational material. Presenting information in visual form on a modern information technology platform without improving the level of figurative thinking and intellectual development will lead to a change in the relationship between figurative and traditional teaching.

This type of teaching, compared to the traditional method, provides information in figurative form corresponding to a new branch of human intellectual development, solving problems related to language communication, and at the same time leads to the development of communication processes in the world. The method of presenting

educational material in the form of pictures can, in one way or another, affect all components of the student's learning process.

In particular, it can be shown that students absorb educational material, understand the meaning, remember and repeat. In addition, this method develops students' emotional approach to reading and ensures that they can master the learning material without much effort. We compare these qualities with traditional and new teaching methods: The presentation of educational material in the form of images provided to students is to a certain extent based on opinion of them, i.e. The text given in literature is re-encoded and memorized. Such a vision requires sufficient time and intellectual ability to create an object model in the student. It is known that talented young people (students) who study this way can get excellent grades.

Most students cannot form an accurate picture of the teaching material provided to them at all times, which is why traditional teaching methods do not provide teaching materials. The level of understanding is still low. In order to present educational materials in the form of images, it is relevant to print them in the form of electronic copies using multimedia tools. The emergence of multimedia tools of information technology and technologies based on them creates an opportunity to solve this problem.

The application of multimedia technologies to the educational process not only frees the pedagogue from complex tasks related to the educational process, but also by introducing text, graphics, animation, and sound elements of visual educational materials that are presented in various forms rich in information gives students the opportunity to deliver. Creating an e-course using multimedia tools not only requires specialist knowledge from teachers but also requires them to have knowledge of computer technology, design, core stories, game play, actors as well as some other knowledge they need to have expertise can be relatively long. For this reason, multimedia courses are often created by a team of experts from different disciplines.

Preparing multimedia lessons requires teachers to be familiar with modern hardware and software tools and be able to use them effectively. For this reason, multimedia courses are created by special teams with software and hardware.

Recently, many research works on computer educational tools have begun to appear, and in most of these works, the authors are mainly interested in the methodological and didactic characteristics of the problem and its analysis.

Analyze the use of electronic educational tools in the educational process almost ignored it. Analysis of existing scientific publications on the creation of electronic information educational resources and their application in the educational process

shows that the problem of using such software tools in the educational process Education has been considered a problem on a global scale and important results have been achieved in this regard.

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